

Analysis of Translation Strategies of Slogans and Translator's Subjectivity Based on Translation Ethics

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Abstract: This research, resorting to Chester man's ethical model of translation, delves into translation strategies of advertising language and combines the characteristics of translator's subjectivity to explore the translator's subjectivity in five ethical models, aiming at exploring to what extent translator's subjectivity has been embodied in the process of translating advertising language under the guidance of translation ethics. Through the analysis, the results show that translation ethics not only limits the translator to the highest normative standards, but also leaves a suitable space for the exertion of translator's subjectivity. However, only under the limit of certain ethics can the translator's subjectivity be displayed to a great extent and achieve the harmony and unity of initiative, passivity and selfishness, thus better disseminating Chinese culture and fostering the smooth communication between Chinese and Western cultures.

Key words: Advertising Language; Translation Ethics; Translation Strategy; Translator's Subjectivity

1. Introduction

With the deepening of economic development after China's accession to the WTO, more domestically produced goods are sold to the international market, and a large number of foreign goods are also pouring into the Chinese market. The competition between commodities is increasingly fierce. As a result, the role of commercial advertising in the promotion of commodity sales and the promotion of market trade has become increasingly evident, and the crucial role of viable advertising translation becomes prominent. However, the reality is that commercial advertising translation has not been widely recognized and fully valued since there isn't a systematic system in the relevant field. What's worse, the translation of some mercantile advertisements is always somewhat unsatisfactory, for instance, the translation of the brand name, instructions, and various commercial advertisements are grammatically and semantically incorrect. Errors in information translation, etc., will not only cause huge economic losses to the enterprise, but also bring serious damage to the reputation. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the translators who are the medium of profitable advertising language to acquire appropriate, systematic and efficient translation theories and strategies to solve numerous problems in commercial advertisement translation so as to regulate and improve the translation of relevant field.

Translation activities are subjective activities and have strong links with ethical concepts. Therefore, the relevant translation ethics can be interpreted as: the moral norms that the relevant translation subjects follow in the translation activities. Because advertisements of different cultures have certain differences in many aspects. Use of specific translation ethics can effectively avoid the problem of improper translation and improve the effect and quality of translation. In 1990, Basnet and Lefever proposed the "cultural turn" of translation studies, and the study of translation from the perspective of macro cultural research laid the diversified and interdisciplinary pattern of translation studies.

In translation, the translator's dual position as translator and writer is clear and consolidated, and the translator's subjectivity is highlighted. However, inappropriate play of the translator's subjectivity has a negative effect on translation. Through research on the translation strategy of slogan and the analysis of translator's subjectivity from the perspective of translation ethics, the importance of "loyalty" in translation ethics is valued. The translator's subjectivity will be exerted under the constraints of translation ethics.

1. A Brief Review of Slogan Translation

French theorist Antoine Berman, from French contemporary, who is the first people to make an ideal

in "translation ethics". He believes that the "legitimate ethical goal" of translation behavior is to respect the creative work and respect the language and cultural differences in the creative work (Berman, 2000: 285-286). Bellman's translation ethical goal actually enriches himself by referring to the "other."

In contrast to Berman, the American deconstruction translation theorist Lawrence Venuti proposed an "alienation" strategy for preserving the differences between the language and culture of the original text. The translation ethical goal is to "promote cultural renewal and change." (Venuti, 1998: 188), against cultural colonialism, against "identity." What Venuti advocates are a type of "reserving ethics" thought, which is actually for the weak language and culture. Anthony Pym first proposed the translator's "interculturality" concept in the 1997 monograph "On the Translator's Ethics". He has a tendency to proceed from the translator's "interculturality" and explores the ethics of translators who promote exchanges and cooperation between different cultures in various forms of translation activities (Wang Dazhi, 2005, 46). In this way, the study of translation ethics has turned to the "translator ethics", that is, the concern about the ethical issues of the translator's profession.

In 1997, the seventh chapter of his published monograph "Memes of Translation: The Spread of Ideas in Translation Theory" specifically explored translation ethics and outlined the outline of translation ethics. Basic categories of translation ethics research are expounded. In 2001, Chesterman wrote Proposal for a Hieronymic Oath, and divided the current translation ethics model, and proposed five ongoing modes of translation ethics. (The Map: A Beginner's Guide to Doing Research in Translation Studies) This paper makes a new summary of the research content covered by translation ethics, and summarizes the scope of translation ethics into four categories: ethics, cultural ideology, practice, and personal and professional ethics.

Mainly studying the translation thought of Italian-American scholar Lawrence Venuti, the translator's stealth means that the translator's trace is not visible in the translation, the so-called "invisibility". The translation should never cause the reader to think they are reading the translation. The translator should either not disturb the author as much as possible, but let the reader move closer to the author (alienation); Compliant translation can be viewed as an ideal strategy for domestication translation. Alienation is based on the aesthetics of incoherence; incoherence can best preserve differences and preserve strangeness.

The reasons why Venuti advocated homogenization translation are this: First: homogenization translation is conducive to the development of multiculturalism, resisting the hegemony of European and American cultures, and protecting cultural ecology. The transformation of indigenous literature; The naturalization school believes that: 1) translation is communication, the translator's responsibility is to avoid cultural conflicts and misunderstandings; 2) naturalization helps readers better Understand the translation;

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Overview of Translation Ethics

1) Ethics and morality have a certain relationship, and translation ethics research should also be different, corresponding to various problems in socialized and ideological translation practice; 2) translation ethics research should be crossed from ethics and translation studies From the perspective of disciplines, the issues of specific social negative impacts in diachronic and synchronic translation practice should be included in the scope of translation "ethics"; 3) theoretical methods should first be clarified in translation studies The typical examples of the "ethics" category of translation should reflect the social directionality, negative directionality and community consensus of ethics. They have a definite objective and provable characteristics, and should not be generalized and generalized. Or over-subjective; 4) translation ethics research is a large category, which should distinguish sub-categories such as "translation ethics", "translator ethics", "translation ethics"; 5) translation ethics researchers should To clarify the purpose and social significance of the research, we should conduct an in-depth and systematic analysis of the specific translation practice issues, and the results of the research have corresponding solutions to the actual translation problems. Interpretation and warning, this is the value of translation ethics research; 6) The selected case and its revealing sociality should have certain universal significance, so it is necessary to grasp the concept when using the concept of translation ethics Essential content, and enable related research to rise from micro-practical understanding to macro-theoretical understanding.

2.2 Chesterman's Five Translation Ethics Models

Andrew Chesterman, the representative of the descriptive translation specification research, is no

exception. In the article "From "Yes" to "Should": Rules, Norms and Strategies in Translation Studies (hereinafter referred to as "From" to "should"", he specifically included the title entitled "ANormativeScience" In the fifth section, the proposed translation study can be regarded as a kind of "normative science", especially the destructiveness of the term "normative" in the term "normative science". In the third chapter of "The Memes of Translation", he devoted two sections to explore "normative vs.

Chesterman, who repeatedly emphasized the purely descriptive nature of his translation normative research, clearly stated in his article "From "Yes" to "Should": "Translation studies must be described and evaluated. This goal can be translated. Standardize research to achieve" (Chesterman, From "is" to "ought" 1). As the title of "From "Yes" to "Should", through the study of translation norms, Chesterman tries to break through the limitations of purely descriptive translation studies that do not contain evaluation factors, "yes" to "should be ". Transition, meeting the dual goals of description and evaluation. He questioned the law of rest that the value judgment could not be logically introduced from the factual judgment. He believed that the "should" of the translation can be drawn from the "yes" of the authoritative professional translator's behavior: "Here, We have an existing 'should': there is already a group of translators and their translations, we think that they (he) embody the norms, from which we can derive for other translators and translations' It should be 'coming.' However, the proposition of "yes" or "no" as a conjunction is a descriptive proposition about facts. The proposition of "should be " or "should not" be a conjunction is a statutory proposition about value. If "what is" can only be the objective statement of the subject without position, then "what should be made" is precisely the subjective requirement of the subject's position. It incorporates the judge's position and attitude and expresses the judge's The desire and value orientation. It is precisely this incorporated position and attitude that form a logical gap between "yes" and "should". Analysis of Slogan Translation Strategies Based on Translation Ethics and Translators' Subjectivity

3.1 Translation Strategies of Advertising Language

3.1.1 Literal translation

Sentence is the basic unit in word-for-word translation, especially in advertising translation. The content that can be completely equivalent should be completely equivalent, and the content that can have not yet been fully equivalent should be roughly equivalent. The goal is to assure both "spirit" and "form". At the same time, considering the constraints of text and context, the sentence structure and rhetoric of the original text should be retained, and the form, content and style of the original text should be reproduced (1). Flowers by interfering speak from the heart. This example of flowers to personify, like a lover to tell the heart, touching.(2) Thirty colors. Some so spectacular they send messages. Some of them are quite strange and carry messages. This example gives the paint a human communicative vagueness and visualizes its function of expressing information.(3) Our eyebrow pencils are as soft as petals. The eyebrow pencil as delicate as petals. (each stroke). This example will eyebrow pencil and petal carry on analogy, it may be said the imagination of genius, highlighted the soft and moving of this product adequately, let the customer appreciate a tender feeling and grace, then heartthrob, the idea of consumption arises spontaneously.(4) Henan. China -- the cradle of kung fu (Henan tourism advertisement). The cradle of Chinese martial art is part of the English language.(5) Yangzi Fridge. I am very proud of you!! Itake pride in you. Yangzi! (Yangzi refrigerator), this example takes Yangzi refrigerator as the object of conversation, directly expressing the emotion of the product, implicitly expressing the excellent quality of the product, and clearly establishing the admirable image of the product.

The literal translation of advertisement is intended to make the source language and target language have cultural commonness and generate the uniform association. It is no longer a word-to-word translation, which requires faithfulness to the deep structure (content) of the original text and consistent with the style of the surface structure (form) of the original text. In other words, advertising translation through literal translation can effectively express the meaning of the original text and take into account the style of the original text. The above sentences is literally translated into the corresponding target language. All the translated sentences retain the basic structure and rhetorical devices of the original sentence, and reproduce the creative mood and rhetorical effect.

3.1.2 Free translation

The "White Feather" pen made in Shanghai, which is translated into "White Feather" in English, has no audience in English-speaking countries. The reason says there is an English idiom "to show the White Feather", which means "to get away from at the last moment", while "White Feather" symbolizes "coward". Still be like now, the American that loves to travel travels more and more, the hotel of Europe and the country such as Latin America, airport, shop USES English to make advertisement in abundance, broadcast announcement, write menu to wait, in order to solicit business, convenient client. Unfortunately, this hospitality often leads to jokes that are hilarious. The funniest joke was an English notice in a hotel in Paris. Americans are so casual. To keep American visitors away from his sumptuous restaurant in slacks, the hotel posted a notice in English: "you can wear a blazer but no trousers!" "These seemingly detached mistranslations are hilarious.

Example 1: original iPhone: Apple reinvents the phone
Thetford phone to beat the iPhone

So, iPhone 3gs: The fastest, most powerful iPhone yet

Example 4: iPhone 4: This changes everything. Again

Example 5: iPhone4s: The most amazing iPhone yet

There are numerous simple sentences, imperative sentences, complex sentences and negative sentences in English advertisements. More active sentences, less passive sentences; Use questions, elliptical sentences, separated sentences; Juxtaposition structure more, less from the principal structure. Chinese advertisements are mainly declarative, with long and complex sentences, but there are also elliptical, imperative and interrogative sentences. In English advertisements, the common rhetorical devices include metaphor, parallelism, parallelism, parallelism, repetition, exaggeration and rhyme, etc. Like English advertisements, Chinese advertisements also use a lot of rhetoric to emphasize the effect. It is difficult to achieve formal equivalence in translating Chinese advertisements into English.

3.1.3 Creative Translation

(1) The slogan "A diamond is forever" for Debeers is translated as "A diamond is forever". The original text is concise and straightforward, which conforms to the exact and concise aesthetic standards of western customers. However, in Chinese culture, advertisements rich in rhythm and momentum and pursuing, the beauty of artistic conception are more favored by clients. With an accurate grasp of the characteristics of Chinese customers, the translator completely subverts the style of the original text without damaging the information of the original text. With bold innovation and the use of end-rhyme rhetoric, the translator makes the advertisement full of verve and lays a good market foundation for the diamond trademark.

(2) Featherwater: light as a feather. The common feature of Featherwater and glass is connected by the slogan "light as a feather". "Fly smooth as silk" is an advertisement of an airline, which compares flight to silk, giving a sense of safety, smoothness and comfort and impressing readers with its exceptional service. EBEL the architects of time. This advertisement USES a metaphorical approach in metaphor, implying that EBEL is the creator of time, which fully embodies the perfection of which and its noble status. Wash the big city out of hair. The AD USES a metonymy technique. Tall city means dirty of hair, which can make people feel surprised and deepen their impression of the shampoo.

(3) The following advertisement: Free hotel! Free meals! Free transfers. For free "remain-on-the-way" in Amstersdam, you can rely in KIM. This advertisement USES 4 Free in a row, which is supposed to be very eye-catching and impressive. It gives people strong stimulation and enhances the effect of advertising to induce people to move forward. And this AD: Whatever you're eating, drinks Maeus Rose. Always LGHT, Always fresh, Always chillies, Always right. The repetition of grammatical structures cannot only emphasize the meaning, but also provide a sense of lightness, confidence and power. = A Dream Price. = A Dream Opportunity. ", which repeats two sentences led by "A Dream" together, greatly enhancing the tone and publicity. Everyone has to know that "everyone is equal before the opportunity". The slogan puts price and opportunity together to show that both are ideal.

(4) Behind that healthy smile, there's a Crest kid. It personifies Crest toothpaste as a person and

makes it have human emotion -- smile, which also implies that as long as the teeth are white and healthy, a confident smile can be brought. Again, such as: Flowers by Interflora speaks from the heart. (Intel florist Flowers say the truth), we know that the flower is not speak, this advertisement gives the characteristics of the people to talk to on the Flowers, more vividly depicts the flower beautiful, delicate and charming make fresh Flowers suddenly rise, it appears to be on behalf of the customer to convey thoughts, greatly enhance the slogan of the advertisement effect. Strong tractor Strong farmer. The tractor AD likens the tractor to an iron giant. Impresses the farmer with what they do and what they do, with what they do.

(5) Ask for More. (More than a mole of cigarettes) Here. This sentence is derived from the nouns in Dickens' novel "The Orphan of the Mist" when Oliver begged for food. More cigarettes take full advantage of the characteristics of their brand names to make a fuss, almost every advertisement has the characteristics of puns. I'm More satisfied (Moore Cigarette, I am more satisfied), the same is the advertisement of Moore Cigarette, More in this advertisement, both as a trademark of cigarettes and as an adverb of modified satisfied, the author cleverly uses the name of the commodity to reach The effect of the pun is very refreshing, and then it is intriguing. There is another ad. Lose ounces, save pounds. The parallel structure and words of this advertisement are easily reminiscent of several idioms of penny and pound, such as Penny wise, pound foolish, which can also be written as Save pennies, lose pounds, in terms of form and above. The ads match, advertisements mean that Golden lay eggs are cheap and good, save money, and don't make people fat, that is, they can help people lose weight.

(6) For example: All roads are expected to result in the Holiday Inn. This slogan is based on the well-known proverb All Roads Lead to Rome. To smoke or not, that's a question, here makes reference to Shakespeare's famous phrase To be or not to be, that's a problem. Attracting people's attention creates a sense of intimacy, and the role of imitation is used here. A Mars day keeps you work. Rest and play. Seeing this chocolate advertisement is a familiar feeling? That's right. This ad imitates an apple a day retains the doctor away in the sentence and the ending, and the combination of work and play is reminiscent of another well-known saying.

(7) Feel good, fast food. (fast food, delicious and warm), in this slogan, good and food both end and rhyme (that is, the sounds of the two sound similar), so that the advertisement reads up and down, the rhythm is neat, creating a sense of beauty. The readers are more convenient to see and remember, and they are full of charm and catchy. Hi-fi, Hi-fun, Hi-fashion, only for Sony, Hi-fi is extremely fine (quality), hi-fun is high-fun, hi-fashion is high-fashion, three compound nouns, Both the pronunciation and the form of the word give a sense of rhythm and intriguing revelation.

The singular purpose of advertising determines its requirement for imaginative translation of translators in terms of style and reading. Faithfully reflects the innovative information to achieve the advertising function of the advertisement, if the effect of the text is boring, it cannot stimulate the reader's recognition and consumer enthusiasm. Translators must not only "translate their meanings" but also "translate their tastes"; while faithfully expressing the meaning of advertisements in a refined and concentrated language, they must convey the charm and beauty of advertisements, so that readers in the culture of translated languages are like enjoying an original Native local advertising. From this point of view, the best effect of advertising translation is that the translator has recreated the translated language of the imaginative content. The vocabulary, syntax and rhetorical features of English advertisements bring a lot of difficulties in the translation of the original text to a certain extent. Therefore, it is necessary to master translation methods and principles when translating.

3.1.4 Transliteration

There is plenty of sun and fresh air for your offspring. (2) Trust us. Over 5000 years of experience. Numerous advertisements play upon the name of the trademark. Puns in brand names can not only increase the interest and sense of humor of advertising, but more importantly, make brand names more attractive to people, easy to remember, and increase the intensity of publicity, so as to achieve the purpose of promoting products. Puns in brand names are mostly homophonic. (3) Translation: "permanent" glass stove will bring you a unique concept: clean. This advertisement promotes its product from any Angle, can arouse the purchase desire of the customer, have certain persuasive effect. Due to cultural differences, semantic inequality exists in Chinese and English languages. Commercial

advertisement translation involves the meaning conversion between two languages and is implemented in the context of cross-cultural communication. If the context features of the source language are distinct from the culture of the target language or are not listed in the culture of the target language, it will result in a certain degree of untranslatability. They are expected to be very fashionable among Chinese businessmen. And there are no four-character idioms in English. When using phonology in advertisements, it can increase the sense of rhythm and rhythm, making the advertisements catchy and catchy. "Want good skin, use big treasure everyday." It's Chinese AD with a rhyme. Hi-Fi, Hi-Fu, Hi-Fashion. Only from Sony. Alliteration rhetoric. If ignored, the translation may bring confusion to readers and even make readers disgusted, resulting in complete marketing failure.

3.2 Translator's Subjectivity Based on Translation Ethics

3.2.1 Ethical Expression Under the Translator's Subjectivity

Chesterman's discussion of the dual goals of description and evaluation through translational norm research began with a review and review of Gideon Toury's translational laws. "Science is science, characterized by the pursuit of the law" (Toury259). The goal of translation theory research based on the additive findings of descriptive translation studies to clarify the intrinsic relationship between various variables related to translation (Toury16), its work "Other" in Descriptive Translation Studies and Others refers to the formation of translation rules. The translation law research here is purely descriptive and empirical. It is built on the observation of the regularity of the actual translation behavior. The basic expression is: under the condition X, the translator (prone) does or does not do Y. In the article "From" to "should", Chesterman first affirmed the view that the translation theory should establish rules for the translation of such human behavior. He refers to the pure descriptive translation law in the figure as "general transitionally", pointing out that this common translation law describes the behavioral tendency of the translator (regardless of its translation ability) under certain conditions, and it involves specific The probability of a particular translation behavior occurring under conditions does not take into account the translator's level and the quality of the translation. He pointed out: "Ordinary translation rules can be made for all types of translators, regardless of their translation capabilities; they can be prepared for any type of translation, as long as the result of such translation is accepted as a 'translation'.

3.2.2 Ethical Services Under the Translator's Subjectivity

The term "alienation" and "planning" mentioned here belongs to the extension of translation at the cultural level. In the authentic translation, it is necessary to take into account the specific cultural background and language habits of the readers, and it is necessary to use the artistic intentions and language intentions accustomed to the relevant personnel for translation. Translation is likewise a culture, and it is necessary to transplant the original language and culture of the target language culture, which can break through the barriers at the language level. The method of homogenization translation emphasizes retaining the cultural background and language characteristics of the imaginative language, so that the target reader can accept the differences and perfect and enrich the target language. In the translation, the target reader needs to understand the corresponding artistic content and reproduce the inventive content of the foreign country. Bellman believes that all cultures resist translation, and the purpose of translation is exercised by language to narrow the relationship. The principal role of advertising is to amend and strengthen people's perceptions, which can lead consumers to consume. If we analyze from the ethics of translation, in the process of Chinese translation, we have to be faithful to the original content in terms of information, so that we can conform to professional ethics and follow the differences. At the same time, it is necessary in order to strengthen the consideration of the target audience and realize the functions and goals of the advertisement. Advertising is a commercial-level term that avoids ignoring the audience in the authentic translation, thus violating the connotation of advertising. In the definite propaganda, it is necessary in order to touch the minds of ordinary customers as much as possible, to resonate, and to achieve the desired publicity effect, and avoid the problem of rejection caused by cultural differences

3.2.3 Ethical Communication Under the Translator's Subjectivity

Translation of English advertisements is not a simple conversion of language content, but also includes consumer psychology and cultural factors, which can be organically combined with translators and audiences. Translators are played by their own subjective initiative. They are actually dancers

wearing handcuffs and anklets. They have an obligation to operate in restrictions and express their creative meaning. Therefore, the translator is obliged to grasp the degree of his personal translation, which is the space that the translator can freely play. Under the premise of not affecting the original meaning, it is necessary to transmit the ingenious advertising culture through content and information function as much as possible, so as to accurately present the content to the audience and related consumers. Creative translation refers to the restriction of the original text, designing new slogans according to the relevant customs and linguistic features of the products, which can make the audience more acceptable. For example, in the advertising of Apple's mobile phone, the expression of Bigger than bigger is utilized, and the translation is limited to large. That is to say. This mobile phone can do a great deal, not only the unprecedented size, but also a lot of additional functional content. If you simply translate it, it is sometimes difficult to take into consideration the characteristics of the phone. In diamond advertising, a diamond is forever is utilized. This kind of expression is relatively simple, and at the same time can reflect the eternal love, can be translated into "diamond long-lasting, a permanent rumor." The popularity of this advertisement is relatively enormous, and the translation effect is also outstanding. The method, of increasing vocabulary not only achieves the symmetry of the structural level, but also reflects the original meaning.

3.2.4 Ethical Principles Under the Translator's Subjectivity

From the perspective of contextual adaptation, the study of the subjectivity of advertising translators is based on the subjectivity of human beings. With the help of the subjective initiative and cultural origins behind the translator's subject, the author grasps the language habits and the translator's social and cultural status. The rational behavior of the behavioral mechanism in translation activities, and a reasonable interpretation of it, thus a deeper exploration of advertising translation theory and practice, in order to enhance the quality of advertising translation.原文: REMY MARTIN XO EXCLUSIVELY FINE CHAMPAGNE COGNAC. 译文: 人头马一开, 好事自然来. Literally speaking, the advertisement translation of Renmao Liquor has nothing to do with the original work, but the translator knows that wine plays a decisive role in Chinese culture: the wine has less than a thousand cups, the wine can be cultivated, and the wine is also one. An effective social means. The translation is not difficult to read, easy to understand, and easy to accept. It not only reflects the utility of the wine, but also conveys the Chinese people's desire to use wine to achieve shared goals and achieve good wishes, which are in line with the clients' inner need. "The translator always determines his own cultural agenda and determines his translation choice and translation strategy according to the needs of the translated language he realizes." The translated text of the advertising translator must adapt to the cultural environment of the translated language, that is, it must have "cultural suitability." Samsung's advertising slogan: Challenge the Limits. This slogan has a distinct meaning and can be translated literally, giving readers the illusion that if you want to challenge your limits, you have to buy Samsung.

The Who, What, When, Where and Y of Basketball Shoes. Here are five Ws (Y is Why). These five words are supposed to be a storytelling news. The point, here is the meaning of "including all the elements", if you have a pair of sport shoes with all functions, would you be prepared to purchase it? The answer is certainly yes. This slogan is very rich and worthy of scrutiny. There is a cigarette slogan: To smoke or not to smoke, that is a problem. It uses Shakespeare's famous phrase "To be or not to be. That is a question". It is more resonating than literal translation. This slogan uses simple and well-known phrases to make consumers feel more intimate and enhance the appeal of advertising and product popularity.

Re-creation translation refers to the fact that it has basically left the scope of translation and is re-created. Motorola expressive communication as: Motorola: wings. (Motorola, leap infinity), "wings" original meaning is "wings, wings", this slogan will extend and expand the meaning of "wings", making it a dual form; modern The advertisement of the car: Prepare to want one. (This is what the public hope, waiting for it). The slogan on the surface means "want to do it", but considering the Chinese expression habit, the four-character is used, and a four-character is in addition to the original meaning. The idiom makes it a twofold form.

The language of translation advertisements should give full play to the language advantages of the translated language, adopt a compliant translation method, and avoid rigid translation. Advertising translation should be like the designer of advertisements, grasping the translation from the perspectives of the operative positioning, language aesthetics and artistic differences of advertisements, without losing the moral feeling that the original advertisements bring to the audience.

(1) Functional positioning translation. Translation of advertisements must grasp the goals and connotations of advertisements, focus on the functions, performance, characteristics and other functional positioning of advertisements, and the functions of products and services as the highlights. For instance, there is a restaurant advertisement: Finest food, most attractive surroundings, and friendly disposition. This slogan caters to customers' requirements for food taste, dining environment and service quality. If translated into "the best food, the most attractive environment, there is a nice reception" is not cool enough to be succinct. If it is translated into "unique flavor, elegant environment, and thoughtful service", it will receive good results, and the characteristics of the restaurant are also consistent with the place.

For instance: Water City, City Water, Jiangnan Scenery, Oriental Style, let us integrate into Suzhou. Go to Suzhou. The city is full of attracting sites. In southern China and it represents the oriental charm. It's your ideal destination for tour. Apparently, the translated sentence 1 seems dull and boring, and the translated sentence 2 shows the beauty of the slogan, making people read catchy.

(3) Cultural corrective translation. Translators should be cognizant of the differences between English and Chinese language culture, pay attention to appropriate cultural transformation and customer psychological adaptability. Chinese culture is deeply shaped by Confucianism. It contains a profound humanistic spirit and forms a Chinese folk psychology with the basic content of "Jiqing" and "Benevolence" as the basic content of the Chinese. Westerners need to be based on the pragmatic and "human-oriented" external tendency psychology. For instance, If you drive, don't drink; If you drink, don't drive. This advertisement reflects comforting characteristics of "respecting personal wishes" in English. If you translate according to the original format and meaning, "If you wish to drive, don't drink alcohol. If you drink alcohol, doesn't drive." This translation will make Chinese readers feel strange and very wrong. Because China is accustomed to express in a compulsory and commanding tone: "Drunk driving is prohibited" to warn the driver that it is not permitted to drive for the sake of the safety of himself and the people on board.

Conclusion

In the current context of economic globalization, the translation of advertising slogans can achieve superior results, share scientific and technological achievements, broaden horizons and let people know about unrelated products. In the tangible translation, it is necessary in order to introduce inexpensive translation strategies, so that the audience can accept the content of the advertisement on the premise of understanding the product. Consequently, translation of English advertising slogans needs to be studied in depth, which is the research content of this study.

As is seen from the above analysis, translator, governed by various ethics, intervenes actively in translation of slogans. Addition of missing information is common in the English translation of slogans in order to make the translation more accessible and comprehensible and such skill is indeed appropriate and proper. Besides, directed by ethics, omission and creative translation are employed to reduce the ambiguity and trouble caused by the cultural difference, which is proved to be effective for the translated version's popularity among receptors.

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